

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF MINI COMPOST MACHINE

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Abstract: Composting, the recycling of organic waste such as vegetation and organic waste reduces the amount of waste going to landfill and is therefore a rapidly growing sector. The residual compost has been described as the stable, sanitized and humus-like material rich in organic matter and free from offensive odors resulting from the composting process of separating collected bio-waste. The approach that we used to complete this project was to divide the project into four main phases that contains multiple tasks within them. Phase one; Composting development Tasks; Composting process and systems, researching composting development. Phase two; Machine design and Requirements. Tasks; Finding an optimum machine design parts, and workshop. Phases Three; Machine construction. Tasks; Building the machine. Phase four; Testing and analysis. Tasks; Operating the machine, checking the performances, Results. Composting is an environmentally friendly method of treating waste which convert organic waste into useful product. Compost has a lot of benefits like: reduce landfill space, reduce surface and groundwater contamination, reduce methane emissions, reduce transportation costs, reduce air pollution from burning waste, provide more flexible overall waste management, enhance recycling of materials and can be carried out with little capital and operating costs. The organic compost machine helps to improve composting and decreases the cost required for degradation, segregation, and transportation etc. of the waste. The flexibility is increased and the total volume of organic waste is minimized. Also, the quality of the compost is determined upon factors such as moisture content, pH, temperature, and time, NPK etc. The organic waste is also a good and healthy compost for agricultural use. Also, it does not have any reverse effect on environment.

Keywords: Recycling organic waste, Compost Machine,

1.INTRODUCTION

Composting, the recycling of organic waste such as vegetation and organic waste reduces the amount of waste going to landfill and is therefore a rapidly growing sector. The residual compost has been described as the stable, sanitized and humus-like material rich in organic matter and free from offensive odors resulting from the composting process of separating collected bio-waste. Recycling is widely assumed to be environmentally beneficial, because allowing organic waste to decay in landfills has a negative impact both environmentally and economically. The Composting is beneficial in soil fertility enhancement, stabilizing the environment, decreasing the global warming, improving the waste management system etc. The composting technique reduces the volume of organic waste and kills the pathogens. Also, organic composting converts the ammonia waste to useful nitrogen rich product. The manure when used in soil increases its fertility. For natural organic composting with the help of micro-organisms, near about 30-40 days required. The segregation is required for natural organic composting but the desirable conditions obtain for micro- organisms to degrade the waste then there will be less time requires for producing organic compost into humus known as a fertilizer. Compost is a key ingredient in organic farming. Compost is rich in nutrients. Composting is enhancing soil fertility as it acts as a soil conditioner, fertilizer, nature pesticides. There are two fundamental types of composting aerobic and anaerobic: Aerobic composting. Composting is the decomposition of organic wastes in the presence of oxygen (air); products from this process include CO₂, NH₃, water and heat. This can be used to treat any type of organic waste but, effective composting requires the right blend of ingredients and conditions. These include moisture contents of around 60-70% and carbon to nitrogen ratios (C/N) of 30/1. Anaerobic composting. Composting is the decomposition of organic wastes in the absence of O₂, the products being methane (CH₄), CO₂, NH₃ and trace amounts of other gases and organic acids. Anaerobic composting was traditionally used to compost animal manure and human sewage sludge.

Figure 1: New technique of waste collection and recycling

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

J. C. Hargraves [1] The recycling of Municipal Solid Waste by using composting is very efficient. The compost can be used for agriculture but it has to be nutrient rich and low metal content. For good quality compost the garbage has to be separated at early stage. The metal content can be increased if sewage sludge is added into the compost. [1] K. R. Talia [2] The management of municipal solid waste can be increased by developing technology or method to convert waste into useful product. The organic waste which is biodegradable can be converted to environmentally friendly organic compost. The organic compost increases soil productivity, decreases environmental pollution and reduces cost. The excess use of chemical fertilizers is hazardous to soil as well as to the environment as it causes water and air pollution. The composting is beneficial as it reduces landfilling, decreases water pollution due to contamination, minimizes the transportation cost etc. The composting is sustainable and wealth generating method. Tom. L. Richard [3] The ideal way to produce compost is by separating the waste, reducing the size and proper mixing. The step by step process has to be done to make good system of composting. While designing the system following factors has to be considered: cost such as operational, maintenance and capital, market for the compost, flexibility etc. Sutripta Sarkar [4] In many cities the proper management of waste is major problem. The organic composting is good way to handle the waste. The heating is self-generated by microorganisms, which produces manure, biogas etc. The degradation process can be accelerated by the thermophilic phase. The moisture has to be about 60% and the temperature is in the range 65°C-67°C. Mohd Sahaid Kalil [5] The landfilling is considered to be used for waste management. But because of it the green-house gases liberate to the atmosphere. The organic waste should be composted to increase the quality of the soil. Ajinkya Hande [6] By using the shredder the organic waste can be chopped to small particles so that proper aeration is done. Due to which the manure is formed in less time and the farmer will get good quality manure at low cost. El-Sayed. G. Khater [7] The chemical and physical properties of manure made from the organic waste is studied. The properties such as porosity, water holding capacity, pH, Carbon: Nitrogen ratio, etc. are studied. The manure quality is depending upon the proportion a physical existence. Christiana.Oa , Adepo S. Olusegunb [8] IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN) www.iosrjen.org ISSN (e): 2250- 3021, ISSN (p): 2278-8719 Vol. 04, Issue 04 (April. 2014), ||V6|| PP 29-33 As families and communities search for safe and effective ways to manage kitchen wastes, composting becomes a more attractive management option, this not only restore value to it but also lead to a reduction in the amount of waste that require disposal. Carmel Carey, Warren Phelan and Conall Boland [9] Environmental RTDI Programme 2000 - 2006 ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION AGENCY Comhshaoil PO Box 3000, Johnstown Castle, Co. Wexford, Ireland. Organic waste (i.e. food and garden waste) constitutes the single largest component (~36%) of household waste. Irish waste management policy requires source separation of organic household waste to divert this material away from landfill to higher treatment options. The preferred sustainable option is to biologically treat organic waste and produce a valuable reusable end product, i.e. compost.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Proposed system One of method of recycling Food and biodegradable waste by compost machine by the process of mechanical biological treatment. • Mechanical biological treatment Mechanical biological treatment is a residual waste treatment process that involves both mechanical and biological treatment. MBT plants were developed with the aim of reducing the environmental impact of landfilling residual waste. MBT therefore compliments, but does not replace, other waste management technologies such as recycling and composting as part of an integrated waste management system. A key advantage of MBT is that it can be configured to achieve several different aims: • Pre-treatment of waste going to landfill. • Diversion of non-biodegradable and biodegradable MSW going to landfill through the mechanical sorting of MSW into materials for recycling and/or energy recovery as refuse derived fuel (RDF). • Stabilization into a compost-like output (CLO)₂ for use on land. • Conversion into a combustible biogas for energy recovery. • Drying materials to produce a high calorific organic rich fraction for use as RDF.

2.1 Effective Ingredients Required for Composting

- Oxygen- It oxidize carbon and hence helps in decomposition process.
- Water- Moisture maintains decomposition activity without causing anaerobic process.
- Nitrogen- Proper proportion of carbon and nitrogen helps in decomposition of material.

2.2 Micro-organisms

- Actino bacteria helps to break bark or papers.
- Protozoa reduces bacteria, fungi and organic particulates by consuming it.
- Rotifers maintain the bacteria and protozoan content in humus.
- Bacteria helps in decomposition of organic material at different levels.
- Fungi such as yeast helps to enhance decomposition process.

2.3 Components of the compost machine.

a. Composting Drum: The composting drum is a small sized cylindrical-shaped hollow solid made of galvanized steel pipe. It is the major container of the waste materials, and it houses the masher with its shaft

b. Shaft: A shaft is a rotating machine element, usually circular in cross section, which is used to transmit power from one part to another, or from a machine which produces power to a machine which absorbs power. e major container of the waste materials, and it houses the masher with its shaft.

Figure.2 a. Composting Drum b. Specifications of composting drum

Figure.3 a Shaft, b. Specification of shaft.

c. DC Motor: A DC motor is rotary device that converts direct current electrical energy into mechanical energy. DC motors are used in applications that the connected load has to have its speed controlled. DC motor helps to run the shaft for mixing of the waste and connected to the mains for the power supply.

Specification.	Type.
Input voltage	12V.
Speed	25rpm
Gear box length	27mm
Power	1.1w

Heater: An electric heating coil used to heat the inner cylindrical drum where composting takes place, which will require a temperature of 70°C. This temperature is being monitored and regulated by a thermostat.

Machine Frame The machine frame consists of the following parts: the outer cylinder (composting drum and chamber), and the heater box. It is supporting element for the compost machine.

Shredder It is a component which is situated on the left top corner of the drum. The function of the shredder is to break the raw materials into tiny chunks. Inside it sits a DC motor fitted with a steel blade which helps in the shredding action. If raw materials are broken into tiny pieces it provides better results

Figure 4 a) Specification of heater, b) Heater c) Machine Frame, d) Ball binder, e) shredder

Water tank This is used to store and heat the water. The heat of the water is transmitted to the inner walls of the cylinder for drying purpose. It also holds the cylinder on it.

Mixer This component mixes all the ingredients inside the cylinder and helps to dry the ingredients evenly. Thermostat This is an electronic device used to maintain the water temperature at 70°C

Figure 5 a)Water Tank, b)Mixer c)Thermostat

2.4 Calculation of Total Power Consumed

Power Consumed by Heater = 1000W/hr

Power Consumed by Thermostat = 12W/hr

Power Consumed by Wiper Motor = 60W/hr

Power Consumed by Shredder for 1Cycle = 9W/Cycle

Total Power Consumed in 24hrs =

$$1000 \times 24 + 12 \times 24 + 60 \times 2 + 9 \text{ (only for 15 min.)}$$

$$24000 + 288 + 120 + 9 = 24,417 \text{ Wh}$$

Figure 6 a) Masher Assembly b) Frame c) Water Tank

Figure 7a) Cylindrical Vessel b) Shredder c) Final Assembly

The block diagram of our designed composting machine, shows how machine works it also shows the main component of the machine and the parameters controlling the machine.

Figure 8 a. Block diagram of the compost machine b. Organic compost machine

Working Process of the Compost Machine.

The organic compost machine is used to degrade the organic waste such as food and garden waste to nitrogen rich organic manure or compost quickly. The temperature and moisture required for degradation of waste with the help of microbial is about 66-75 respectively. The proper management of temperature and moisture content decreases the time period required for composting. Due to which the segregation and improper landfilling is restricted. The composting machine consists of a composting drum made from mild steel, and is enclosed by an outer cylinder mounted directly on a frame. A feeding of waste and additive enters from outside through the cylindrical enclosure into the composting drum. The outer cylinder bears a box on one of its sides. This box houses a heating coil mounted just behind it. Heat is produced by an electrically controlled heating coil, regulated by a thermostat, which warms up the air in the box, together with air coming from outside through an opening created at the back of the box. This heated air, by means of convection heat transfer, warms up the inner cylinder/composting drum in which the waste materials to be composted are stored in order to achieve a slow drying of the materials. A 12mm diameter shaft passing through the center of the composting drum horizontally and spans through the length of the composting drum inside, on which a masher is being driven by a 0.5HP geared motor with an average output speed of 25rpm. The masher does the task of mashing the waste materials against the inner walls of the composting cylinder. Simultaneously, the mashing, mixing and the low-heat addition (drying) processes occur over a period to achieve the desired result. The obtained compost was reduced to 70-80% of the initial amount of the organic waste.

Additives:

BIOCULUM • Manufacture – EXCEL INDUSTRIES. -Accelerates aerobic composting of organic, kitchen and garden waste. Produces bio-stabilized organic manure, free from pathogens, foul smell and weed seeds.

SANITREAT ODOUR CONTROL. Powerful odour control agent. One stop solution to your smelly waste

Bioculum and Sani treat

Cost Estimation:

Budget	Amount (Rs)
Metal vessel	4000
Heater	600
Shaft	400
Masher assembly	400
Bearing	300
DC Motor	2500
Machine frame	500
Labor	2000
Additives	500
Miscellaneous	1500
Total	12,700

Figure 9. Fabrication

Parameters Effecting Performance of Composting: There are a wide range of parameters which can be used to monitor physical, chemical, biological, and biochemical variations during composting, such as the aeration rate, temperature, pH, moisture content, carbon/nitrogen (C/N) ratio, respiration, enzyme activity, microbial colony, and bioassay. Temperature is an important factor for evacuating composting efficiency. It can affect microbial metabolism, population dynamics (e.g., composition and density) of microbes and diversity of microorganisms, and thus can be considered as a promising index of microbial activities and bio-oxidative stages pH Another important environmental factor is the pH value of composting materials. The presence of short chain organic acids in raw materials, mainly lactic and acetic acids. The degradation of organic waste increases the concentrations of organic acids which are intermediate by-products of microbial breakdown of easily degraded substrates such as sugars, fats, starch, and greases during the initial phase of composting. Low pH as a result of organic acids most of the time opposes progress of composting process. The C/N ratio is one of the most important parameters to control the composting process and to determine the feedstock recipe and the degree of maturity of the end product of compost. The nutrient that has received the most attention in composting systems is nitrogen since it is the most needed element for plant nutrition. Moreover, it has often been recognized as a limiting factor for microbial growth and activity during the decomposition of plant residues especially in materials with a high C/N ratio. Moisture content Microbial activity and the physical structure in the composting process can be affected by moisture content; also, it has a central influence on the biodegradation of organic materials. Moisture content is one of the critical designs and operating parameters used in compost engineering systems. It is important to transport dissolved nutrients required for the physiological and metabolic activities of microorganisms. Moisture works as a medium to transfer dissolved gas and nutrients absorbed through the cell membrane of micro-organisms. The water during composting is produced as a by-product of microbial activities; also, the generated heat through degradation will dry up part of the moisture. The moisture content can be adjusted by blending of components or by adding water. The aeration rate is the one of most important parameters for the composting process. The main purposes of air supply to composting is to provide oxygen for biological degradation, dry up the wet materials and remove excess moisture, and to carry off exhaust gas and generated heat. Air flow influences spatial distribution

of gases, moisture, temperature, and the decomposition rate of the organic matter. The aeration provides oxygen to inhibit anaerobic condition and support the aerobic activity.

Figure 10 a) Without Compost b) With compost

4.CONCLUSION

Composting is an environmentally friendly method of treating waste which convert organic waste into useful product. Compost has a lot of benefits like: reduce landfill space, reduce surface and groundwater contamination, reduce methane emissions, reduce transportation costs, reduce air pollution from burning waste, provide more flexible overall waste management, enhance recycling of materials and can be carried out with little capital and operating costs. The organic compost machine helps to improve composting and decreases the cost required for degradation, segregation, and transportation etc. of the waste. The flexibility is increased and the total volume of organic waste is minimized. Also, the quality of the compost is determined upon factors such as moisture content, pH, temperature, and time, NPK etc. The organic waste is also a good and healthy compost for agricultural use. Also, it does not have any reverse effect on environment.

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